

Prevalence of Malocclusion and Orthodontic Treatment Needs in Children with and without Special Health Care needs: A Comparative Cross-Sectional Study

Prachi Mujariya¹, Arunkumar Sajjanar², Shyam Chandak³, Shabdali Waghmare⁴,
Manali Khole⁵, Gauri Patil⁶

Department of Pediatric and Preventive Dentistry, Maharashtra University of Health Sciences

Abstract

The prevalence of malocclusion in India varies from 20-43 %. It has a great impact on society and individuals in terms of quality of life, discomfort, social and functional limitations. It has been shown to affect oral health, increase prevalence of dental caries and cause TMJ disorders. The benefits of taking orthodontic treatment are to prevention of tissue damage, correction of aesthetic component and improve physical function. The aim of this study is to find out the prevalence of malocclusion and orthodontic treatment needs in children with visual impairment, hearing impairment, and without any special health care needs and to make them aware of importance of orthodontic treatment. This cross-sectional study includes 240 children, 60 with visual impairment, 60 with hearing impairment and 120 with no special health care needs in the age group of 6- 14 yrs. The class of malocclusion was observed using Angle's system of classification and primary molar relationship. The DAI (Dental aesthetic index) which consists of 10 parameters is recorded clinically in children of both groups and a DAI score is calculated using a regression equation. It is used to rank malocclusion according to the level of severity and orthodontic treatment needs following the WHO criteria. Class II and Class III MO was found more common in Group III and Group II. The DAI mean scores were highest in Group II, with no significant difference. Statistically significant difference was found in grade 4 MO. Individuals with SHCN had higher need of urgent orthodontic treatment compared to children without SHCN.

Keywords- prevalence, malocclusion, special health care needs, orthodontic treatment needs.

I. Introduction

Children with special health care needs require dentist's special attention as they most often fail to maintain proper oral hygiene leading to various dental problems.¹ Several studies have reported that around 50-70% of special needs population find difficulty in accessing dental care.¹ Reasons for this can be lack of dental awareness, difficulty in communication and lack of specialized dentists and their own low level of expectations from oral healthcare services.⁶

In general oral pathologies are more common in special needs patients than general population.¹ Among these malocclusion is ranked third.⁵ A literature search reveals the prevalence of malocclusion in India varies between 19.6% to 55.3%. It has a great impact on society and individuals in terms of quality of life, discomfort, social and functional limitations.² It has been shown to affect oral health, increase prevalence of dental caries, affects deglutition patterns, phonetics and can cause TMJ disorders.³ The reasons for development of malocclusion can be genetic or environmental and/or combination of both along with various local factors such as adverse oral habits, tooth anomalies, form and developmental position of teeth.³

Special health care needs (SHCN) children belong to high-risk group which usually suffers from various medically untreated diseases, have a significant impact on their general health adding to the negligence

in maintaining oral health due to their potential motor, sensory, and intellectual disabilities.⁶ Thus, making the functions of oral cavity like chewing, swallowing and speech difficult for them resulting in malocclusion.⁴

The children affected with the partial or complete loss of hearing and partial or complete loss of vision and those who are dumb all have problems related to understanding and maintaining the oral hygiene instructions and practices in comparison to their normal counterparts. Poor oral hygiene maintenance may cause the premature loss of the teeth and subsequently lead to the development of malocclusion.⁵ Hearing disorders affect the general behavior and impair the level of social functioning. This group is often neglected because of ignorance, fear, stigma, misconception and negative attitudes.⁶

The advantages of taking orthodontic treatment are not only improvement of physical functions but also prevention of soft tissue damage, along with correction of aesthetic components of individual. Considering these factors, the Dental Aesthetic Index (DAI), which is recommended by the World Health Organization (WHO) as a rapid and relatively simple method of assessing dento-facial anomalies, was developed. The DAI is an orthodontic index that links clinical and aesthetic components mathematically to produce a single score. It also aims to predict the clinical judgments of orthodontists by separating handicapping and non-handicapping malocclusions.⁷

The assessment of orthodontic treatment needs is helpful for dental public health programs for screening of patients requiring urgent orthodontic treatment and planning treatment procedure and resources or funding for the same.⁸ Little attention has been paid to SHCN children particularly in Nagpur rural region.

Search of literature revealed no studies comparing the prevalence of malocclusion in visual, hearing impairment and general population children. Hence, the present study was undertaken to comparatively assess the distribution, prevalence and severity of malocclusion and orthodontic treatment needs at the age of 6 to 14 years children with and without SHCN in randomly selected rural Nagpur population using DAI.

II. Materials And Methods

The study included 300 children, 200 with SHCN and 100 without SHCN in the age group of 6-14 years. Among 200 SHCN, 100 were visually impaired and 100 were dumb and deaf or with hearing impairment. Sample size is determined considering the difference in mean DAI scores in two groups.

Following formula was used for estimating the sample size:

Formula

$$n = \frac{2 S^2 (Z_{1-\alpha} + Z_{1-\beta})^2}{\delta^2}$$

Where,

S_1 : Standard deviation in the first group

S_2 : Standard deviation in the second group

$$S^2 = (S_1^2 + S_2^2) / 2$$

$$\text{Mean difference (Effect size)} = (\mu_1 - \mu_2)$$

A = Significance level

$$1 - \beta = \text{Power}$$

Children were randomly divided into 3 groups:

Group I: Visually impaired children

Group II: Dumb and deaf children

Group III: Children without special health care needs.

The group with visual impairment were selected from Dynan Jyoti Mahavidyalaya, hearing impairment from Mukhbadhir Mahavidyalaya and general population from Mahatma Gandhi Mahavidyalaya, which all lie in the Nagpur rural region. The study was carried out between January to April 2023. The study protocol was approved by the Institutional ethical committee of SDKS dental college and hospital. After obtaining permission from each schools involved, informed consent was obtained from each individual or caregiver. To be eligible for this study the participants had to fulfil the following inclusion criteria:

Common criteria: 1] Age should be between 6 to 14 yrs.

2] No previous history of orthodontic treatment.

Group 1: 1] Patients having mild, moderate or severe visual acuity or blindness.

Group 2: 1] Patients having mild, moderate, severe or profound audiometric ISO value including deafness and dumbness.

Exclusion criteria was: 1] Presence of other disabling conditions such as cerebral palsy, downs syndrome or autism.

A prestructured questionnaire was filled to record clinical index and sociodemographic data – name, age, gender, type of disabling conditions, brushing habits, any other habits. The clinical examinations were performed in the respective schools by single observer to avoid data collection bias. The clinical observations were carried out in the school under natural lighting, using a mouth mirror number 4 and a periodontal probe. The DAI was used to rank MO according to the level of treatment need, following the WHO criteria, and the class of occlusion was observed using the Angle system of classification. The DAI consists of 10 parameters according to three components: missing teeth, spacing/crowding, and occlusion. The global value of DAI was calculated for each individual using a regression equation.

Each subject's DAI score were tabulated in excel sheet according to the severity of MO in a four grade scale. A score lower than or equal to 25 means normal occlusion or slight MO not needing orthodontic treatment. A score between 26 and 30 is categorized as definitive MO with treatment elective. A score between 31 and 35 is categorized as severe MO with treatment

highly desirable, and a score equal or higher than 36 is categorized as very severe handicapping MO under mandatory treatment.

Statistical analysis:

Data was coded and analysed with the statistical software, STATA, version 10.1 (2011) by Stata Corp. Texas, USA. Descriptive Statistics was calculated e.g summary measures like Mean, Standard Deviation for quantitative variables and frequency/percentages for qualitative (Categorical) variables. Inferential statistics include P-values from hypothesis testing procedures. Between-the-group comparisons of mean difference across 3 groups for quantitative outcome variables was evaluated with ANOVA (Analysis of variance) procedures with F test. Pearson’s Chi-square test and Z test for difference in proportions was performed for comparing difference in proportions in three groups for qualitative (Categorical) parameters. A P-value less than 0.05 was considered statistically significant for all the comparisons.

III. Results

1] The Angle’s class of MO revealed that class I was presented in 66% of cases in Group I, 65% in Group II and 61% in group III. Class II was presented in 26% of cases in Group I, 24% in Group II and 29% in Group III . Class III was presented in 8% cases in Group I, 11% in Group II and 10% in Group III. Class II MO was found to be more common in Group III individuals and class III was much more prevalent in Group II, no statistical difference was found between groups. (Figure 1)

Figure 1: Prevalence of Angle’s class of malocclusion among three groups.

2] The DAI mean value for all the participants was 29.95 with the lowest value of 7 and a maximum of 49. The means of the Group I, II and III are presented in Table 1. The DAI mean scores were highest in Group II> Group I> Group III with p value of 0.1364, that is no significant difference in mean DAI scores across 3 groups. (Table 1)

Table 1- Groups	n	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	SD	P value (by ANOVA)
Group 1	100	12	49	30.29	6.69	F =2.01, DF=(2, 297) P- 0.1364 Interpretation Overall: No significant difference in mean DAI scores across 3 groups
Group 2	100	16	47	30.66	6.00	
Group 3	100	7	49	28.90	6.93	
Total	300	7	49	29.95	6.58	

Table 1: Mean DAI scores for all the three groups and p value showing no significant difference found in between the groups.

3] Around 48 children of the study population presented a score lower than 25 in DAI (grade 1), implicating very little or no need of orthodontic treatment. From all study population, Group I presented the highest percentage of individuals with the most extreme values of the scale, 46 in grade 2 and in 14 in grade 4, meaning very severe or handicapping MO. On the contrary, Group II presented highest number children with very severe type of MO compared to other groups. All the three groups showed statistically significant difference in grade 4 or very severe MO (Table 2).

Table 2: Number of participants(n) falling under different grades of malocclusion and corresponding treatment needs based on DAI scores among three groups. Statistically significant difference found in three groups under

Table 2- DAI severity levels	DAI treatment needs	Group I	Group II	Group III	Total	P value (by ANOVA)
Grade 1-Normal/minor malocclusion DAI score ≤25	No treatment need or slight need	n=12 20.8±4.6	n=14 21.6±3.7	n=22 19.5±4.1	n=48 20.5±4.1	0.3003 Not Significant
Grade 2-Definitive malocclusion DAI score = 26-30	Treatment elective	n=46 27.3±1.3	n=36 27.5±1.3	n=37 27.7±1.7	n=119 27.5±1.5	0.6712 Not Significant
Grade 3-Severe malocclusion DAI score = 31-35	Treatment highly desirable	n=28 32.9±1.1	n=31 33.1±1.2	n=31 32.9±1.1	n=90 33.0±1.1	0.6880 Not Significant
Grade 4-Very Severe malocclusion DAI score = ≥36	Treatment mandatory	n=14 42.8±4.5	n=19 39.4±2.9	n=10 41.7±3.7	n=90 41.0±3.9	0.0339 Significant
Total		n=100 30.3±6.7	n=100 30.7±6.0	n=100 28.9±6.9	n=300 29.9±6.5	0.1364 Not Significant

grade 4 or very severe type of malocclusion requiring mandatory orthodontic treatment.

4] The comparison of frequency and percentage of severity levels of malocclusion or grades of treatment needs based on DAI scores in all the 3 groups (Table 3). It shows that there is significant difference in the p value of no treatment needs between group 1 and 3, group 3 has majority children which require no or slight orthodontic treatment. Other groups have not shown any significant differences of frequency and percentage distributions of orthodontic treatment needs based on DAI severity levels.

Table 3- DAI severity levels	DAI treatment needs	Group 1	Group 2	Group 3	Pairs	P value (Pair-wise comparisons)
Normal/minor malocclusion DAI score ≤ 25	No treatment need or slight need (n=48)	12 (25%)	14 (29.17%)	22 (45.83%)	1 vs 2 1 vs 3 2 vs 3	0.6741 0.0598 0.1409
Definitive malocclusion DAI score = 26-30	Treatment elective (n=119)	46 (38.66%)	36 (30.25%)	37 (31.09%)	1 vs 2 1 vs 3 2 vs 3	0.1505 0.1965 0.8832
Severe malocclusion DAI score = 31-35	Treatment highly desirable (n=90)	28 (31.11%)	31 (34.44%)	31 (34.44%)	1 vs 2 1 vs 3 2 vs 3	0.6418 0.6418 1.0000
Very Severe malocclusion DAI score = ≥ 36	Treatment mandatory (n=43)	14 (32.56%)	19 (44.19%)	10 (23.26%)	1 vs 2 1 vs 3 2 vs 3	0.3408 0.3841 0.0707

Table 3: Comparison of frequency and percentage of severity levels of malocclusion or grades of treatment needs based on DAI scores in all the 3 groups

IV. Discussion

DAI has been used in this study because of clarity and recurrently used in epidemiological studies.¹ When compared with one of the most commonly used index, the Index of Orthodontic Treatment Need (IOTN), which has the same goal as DAI in identification of children most in need of orthodontic treatment, DAI has the advantage that perceptions of aesthetics are linked with anatomical trait measurements to produce a single score, obviating the need for two separate instruments that cannot be combined as in the IOTN. IOTN uses only three grades and thus lacks the ability to rank order cases with greater or lesser need for treatment within grades. In contrast, DAI scores can be rank ordered on a continuous scale and can differentiate cases within severity levels.⁶

Orthodontic treatment in SHCN individuals has long been neglected. Indeed, it can be difficult to communicate with and obtain cooperation from these patients, but the variation of the degree of intellectual is extremely wide, rendering, in more severe cases, to an unfeasibility of treatment.¹

19% of dumb and deaf children required mandatory orthodontic treatment. Jackson was amongst the first to broach the issue of orthodontic treatment for children with disabilities. He suggested that treatment should still be undertaken, although 'ideal' results may not always be possible. Decisions on orthodontic therapy should include consideration of the extent to which the malocclusion handicaps the individual.⁹ Even if an ideal orthodontic result is not possible, compromises can be achieved in guiding the developing occlusion for those with tooth-size/arch-size discrepancies or abnormal exfoliation or eruption patterns. Well timed extractions may produce an acceptable occlusion without other therapy or with the addition of a simple appliance.¹⁰

Becker et al. found that fixed appliances were more difficult for children with disabilities to tolerate compared with the use of removable appliances.¹¹ By contrast, Chadwick and Asher¹² McDade recommended the use of fixed appliances, even for simple tipping mechanics, since, they maintained, the tooth movements can be accomplished more simply and rapidly. Provision of orthodontic care is important and should be appropriate to the child's needs and demands, and not driven by unrealistic parent aspirations. At the same time, efforts should be directed towards correcting significant malocclusions where psychological harm in an already compromised child may be an additional and unnecessary burden.⁹

The highest prevalence of malocclusion worldwide is found during the deciduous dentition period (54%) and follows in permanent dentition (54%). Based on these prevalence data, malocclusion has been recognized as the relevant oral health problem causing economic burden for both the family of affected children as well as dental health public services. Paediatricians, health care workers and dentists should be trained for preventive strategies (like maintaining oral hygiene habits) or early diagnosis and appropriate orthodontic treatment strategies to prevent malocclusion onset at an early stage.¹³

This study had less sample size so there is need to further assess the prevalence of malocclusion and orthodontic treatment needs in children with and without SHCN on a large population. Again, this study covered only the Nagpur rural area so there is need to extent the area of focus.

V. Conclusion

This study compared the prevalence of Angle's class of malocclusion, DAI mean scores and severity or grade of MO and urgency of orthodontic treatment needs in children with and without SHCN in the age group of 6-14 years.

The results of this study demonstrate that individuals with SHCN had higher need of orthodontic treatment and a higher prevalence of more urgent treatment compared to children without SHCN.

It appeared that a relatively high proportion of the children in our study did not currently receive or had not yet received any form of professional oral care. This suggests that there is a need for renewed collaborative efforts by the various health disciplines and social service agencies to increase access to dental services for these children.

The information of the distribution of MO in the population with and without special health care needs provides us a knowledge base to be used in future comparisons, orienting decision making, treatment planning, and public health policies.

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